

**MATERNAL SLEEP QUALITY INDEX FOR THE THIRD TRIMESTER
(MSQI-T3-ID) QUESTIONNAIRE**

Instructions:

Please mark (✓) the option that best describes your condition during the past week.

No.	Question	Never	Rarely	Often	Always
		1	2	3	4
Dimension 1 – Sleep Initiation & Continuity (SIC)					
1	I have difficulty falling asleep at night.				
2	I frequently wake up during the night and have difficulty falling back asleep.				
3	I feel that my sleep at night is not restful.				
Dimension 2 – Pregnancy-Specific Disturbance (PSD)					
4	My sleep is disturbed due to back pain, abdominal discomfort, or other physical discomforts related to pregnancy.				
5	My sleep is disturbed because I need to urinate frequently during the night.				
6	My sleep is often disturbed because I have difficulty finding a comfortable sleeping position.				
Dimension 3 – Daytime Impact & Fatigue (DIF)					
7	I feel excessively tired or sleepy during the daytime.				
8	Poor sleep at night interferes with my daily activities the following day.				

Reference :

Jannah, N., & Selvarajh, G. (2026). Multidimensional Structure Of Maternal Sleep Quality In The Third Trimester: Psychometric Evaluation. *International Journal of Public Health Excellence (IJPHE)*, 5(2), 47–54. <https://doi.org/10.55299/ijphe.v5i2.1798>

**LATE PREGNANCY ANXIETY SCALE (LPAS)
QUESTIONNAIRE**

Instructions:

Please mark (✓) the option that best describes your condition during the past week.

No.	Question	Never	Rarely	Often	Always
		1	2	3	4
Fear of Childbirth Process (Labor-Related Anxiety)					
1	I feel worried when thinking about the childbirth I will go through.				
2	I worry that I will not be able to cope with the pain of labor.				
3	I worry that I may lose control during childbirth.				
Dimension 2 – Fetal Safety Concerns (Baby-Related Anxiety)					
4	I worry about my baby’s safety as childbirth approaches.				
5	I am afraid that my baby may develop serious health problems.				
6	I worry that my baby may not survive during or shortly after delivery.				
Dimension 3 – Maternal Self-Doubt & Psychological Readiness Anxiety					
7	I feel mentally unprepared to face childbirth.				
8	I worry that I am not strong enough to go through the childbirth process.				

Reference :

Jannah, N., & Selvarajh, G. (2026). Late-pregnancy anxiety as a distinct multidimensional construct: Psychometric evidence from a community-based sample. *Science Midwifery*, 13(6), 1562–1570. <https://doi.org/10.35335/midwifery.v13i6.2230>

**CHILDBIRTH READINESS QUESTIONNAIRE (CRQ)
QUESTIONNAIRE**

Instructions:

Please mark (✓) the option that best describes your condition during the past week.

No.	Question	Never	Rarely	Often	Always
		1	2	3	4
Physical–Cognitive Readiness					
1	I feel that my body is physically prepared to undergo the childbirth process.				
2	I have prepared essential arrangements for childbirth, including the delivery facility, necessary supplies, and transportation.				
3	I feel confident in making appropriate decisions when labor begins.				
Psychological–Spiritual Readiness					
4	I feel calm when facing the upcoming childbirth.				
5	I am able to accept the childbirth process as an experience I am mentally prepared to undergo.				
6	My personal beliefs or spirituality help me feel more prepared for childbirth.				
7	I feel that I have inner strength to go through the childbirth process, regardless of what may occur.				
Social Support Readiness					
8	I have a close person who is ready to accompany me during labor.				
9	I feel that I receive sufficient support from my family or partner in preparing for childbirth.				

Reference :

Jannah, N., & Selvarajh, G. (2026). Development and Pilot Testing of a Childbirth Readiness Questionnaire (CRQ) for Third-Trimester Pregnant Women In Indonesia. *International Journal of Public Health Excellence (IJPHE)*, 5(2), 1–8.
<https://doi.org/10.55299/ijphe.v5i2.1739>

QUESTIONNAIRE
KNOWLEDGE PREGNANT WOMEN

Danger Signs & Care-Seeking

- 1. Vaginal bleeding during the third trimester of pregnancy should be:**
 - A. Waited until it stops on its own
 - B. Treated with traditional remedies
 - C. Immediately evaluated by a healthcare professional
 - D. Considered normal before labor

- 2. If fetal movements noticeably decrease within one day, a pregnant woman should:**
 - A. Rest and wait until the next day
 - B. Drink warm fluids to stimulate movement
 - C. Seek medical care promptly
 - D. Ignore it if there is no pain

- 3. Severe abdominal pain accompanied by fever in late pregnancy indicates:**
 - A. A normal condition before labor
 - B. A danger sign requiring medical attention
 - C. Common maternal fatigue
 - D. Normal hormonal changes

Birth Preparation & Planning

- 4. The main purpose of selecting a delivery facility during the third trimester is to:**
 - A. Follow family traditions
 - B. Ensure timely access to skilled care during labor
 - C. Reduce delivery expenses
 - D. Avoid antenatal visits

- 5. An important preparation for potential obstetric emergencies is:**
 - A. Purchasing baby clothes
 - B. Arranging transportation to a healthcare facility

- C. Reducing physical activity
- D. Increasing sleeping hours

6. Preparing maternal and newborn supplies before labor aims to:

- A. Comply with family expectations
- B. Prevent last-minute delays during childbirth
- C. Decrease antenatal check-ups
- D. Replace professional healthcare services

Preventive Care Before Birth

7. Regular antenatal care visits during the third trimester help to:

- A. Determine the baby's sex
- B. Detect pregnancy-related complications early
- C. Reduce nausea symptoms
- D. Prevent normal vaginal delivery

8. Taking iron supplements during pregnancy is intended to:

- A. Increase maternal body weight
- B. Prevent low blood pressure
- C. Prevent anemia
- D. Reduce labor pain

Maternal Conditions Affecting Labor

9. High blood pressure during pregnancy may result in:

- A. Faster normal labor
- B. An increased risk of delivery complications
- C. Consistently large newborns
- D. No effect on labor outcomes

10. Maternal anemia during pregnancy may lead to:

- A. Uncomplicated childbirth
- B. Severe fatigue and postpartum hemorrhage
- C. Earlier onset of labor
- D. Temporary reduction in fetal movement

Reference :

Jannah, N., & Selvarajh, G. (2026). Development of the Third-trimester Pregnancy Knowledge Questionnaire (TPKQ): A Pilot Study. *International Journal of Public Health Excellence (IJPHE)*, 5(2), 9–17. <https://doi.org/10.55299/ijphe.v5i2.1740>